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Teacher Support **अध्यापक साथी**

**An Initiative
for
Professional Development of Teacher Educators**

**National Council for Teacher Education
New Delhi**

अध्यापक साथी

राष्ट्रीय अध्यापक शिक्षा परिषद् (राअशिप) द्वारा प्रवर्तित अध्यापक साथी भारत तथा भारत के बाहर आवासित अध्यापक शिक्षा के कर्णधारों को सम्बोधित है। इसका उद्देश्य शिक्षा विशेषतौर से अध्यापक शिक्षा में गुणवत्ता की चिन्ता को मुखर करना है। राअशिप जो देश में अध्यापक शिक्षा व्यवस्था के नियोजित एवं समन्वित विकास को सुकर बनाने तथा मानकों एवं मानदण्डों को सुनिश्चित करने हेतु एक शीर्षस्तरीय विधिक निकाय के रूप में गठित एवं संकल्पबद्ध है, उन नवाचारी विचारों एवं अवधारणाओं को प्रसारित करने का आधार प्रदान करती है जो शैक्षिक प्रक्रियाओं में गुणवत्ता के मुद्दों को उजागर करने में सहायक होंगी। अध्यापक शिक्षा के लिए समर्पित यह पत्रिका मूल्य-आधारित शिक्षा, सूचना एवं सम्प्रेषण प्रौद्योगिकी के उभरते नूतन आयाम जो शिक्षण-अधिगम के प्रतिमान से प्रत्यक्षतः सम्बद्ध हों, गुणवत्तापूर्ण अध्यापक शिक्षा के शाश्वत् चिन्ताओं के संदर्भ में लेख, प्रतिवेदन, शोधपरक एवं अन्वेषणात्मक अध्ययनों के सारांशों की प्रस्तुति साग्रह आमंत्रित करती है।

Teacher Support

The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has launched Teacher Support which is addressed to Teacher Educators in India and abroad. Its intent is to promote the quality concerns in education specially in teacher education. In consonance with the vision and mandate of the NCTE as an Apex Statutory Body for facilitating planned and co-ordinated development of teacher education system in the country and for ensuring maintenance of norms and standards, it is felt imperative to disseminate innovative ideas and concepts which will strengthen the cause of quality in educational processes. Devoted as it is to teacher education, the journal invites articles, reports and summary of research and investigative studies particularly in the context of value-based education, emerging new horizons of ICT with bearing on new teaching-learning paradigms and the perennial concerns for quality teacher education.

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Teacher Support
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Professional Development of Teacher Educators

गुरुर्गुरुतमो धाम
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National Council for Teacher Education
New Delhi

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[हिन्दी खण्ड]

“उच्च प्राथमिक स्तर पर सतत् एवं समग्र मूल्यांकन प्रणाली: यथास्थिति, समस्याएँ एवं विद्यार्थियों के सर्वांगीण विकास पर प्रभाव”	डॉ. एन.एन.जी. माथुर डॉ. अनिता सोजतिया	61
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Learning Difficulties in Fractions and Decimals: A Study on Upper Primary School Students

Prof. R.G. Kohari*
Dr. H.S. Mistry**

Mathematics contributes a great deal in the development and research of all disciplines. It deals with the numerical, calculation and reasoning part of a man's life and knowledge. Arithmetic is the foundation of mathematical knowledge which is commonly understood as the art of computation and its application. Fraction is one of the important concepts in arithmetic that has occupied a key position in the school curriculum. In the beginning years of the schooling, it is taught to provide competence in performing the fundamental operations with the numbers, as these are required in the life or in the community. Students tend to view fractions as isolated digits, treating the numerator and denominator as separate entities that can be operated on independently. A major source of difficulty for students' learning in fraction is a fact that a fraction can have a multiple meanings - part/whole, decimals, ratios, or quotients. Students' understanding of fractions are very rote, limited and dependent, on the representational form. So, diagnosis of their difficulties in fraction at primary stage can be beneficial as it may provide necessary remedy. The authors carried out a study on learning difficulties in fraction and decimal. A diagnostic type test was constructed and administered on the upper primary school students. It was found that students were facing difficulties in some concepts of fraction and decimal. Based on their difficulties, the authors discussed and suggested remedies.

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** Research Assesstant

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Introduction

Arithmetic, the foundation of mathematical knowledge, is commonly understood as the art of computation and its application. Fraction is one of the important concepts in arithmetic that is central to the understanding of mathematics in general. In the beginning years of the schooling, it is taught to provide competence in performing the fundamental operations with the numbers, as they are required in the life or in the community. Frequently in the upper grades in particular, the concept and the processes of the other branches of mathematics such as algebra and geometry enter into the applications of fraction. Thus any type of new knowledge may be developed, only when concept of the fraction is clearly understood. Mathematics, taught in upper primary school level, contains major portion of fraction and its application. Also the geometrical calculations such as length, breadth, or area etc. are all based on and are calculated with the help of fractions. Therefore, the investigators considered that investigating weakness in fractions will benefit the other braches of mathematics and thus overall achievement in school mathematics may be improved. The basic aim of fraction is to equip the pupil with understanding of the nature and use of the number system in daily life, and with the ability to use the knowledge for the development of society. Pupils, who cannot grasp the fundamental of fractions, find difficulty in understanding the higher mathematics. If the reasoning power in fraction is not properly developed in the mind of the pupils, it is difficult for them to understand the logic, which is an essential component of learning mathematics. So the learning of fractions at upper primary school stage has a great effect on learning of it at higher stage. According to Rastogi (1991), "much of the problem of failure of students in mathematics, particularly at the elementary level is due to the lack of their mastery of the basic concept of fraction and operations to carry out in solving the fractions such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division and inadequate development of their reasoning abilities". Even when a learner can competently perform these basic operations, he or she may not be able to correctly solve the problem given in the form of a story, or to choose the right operation in the given case. Reason is therefore, often termed as fourth R after the three Rs of reading, writing and arithmetic. With the rapid development of cognitive science in recent years, various methods have been developed by researchers in mathematics education to understand the root cause of the difficulties of the under achievers. One of the simple techniques of determining the specific learning difficulties of individual students is to analyze the specific errors committed by them individually in the successive stages of solving problem. The primary purpose of the test prepared by the investigators is to know how well the student had mastered the basic skills in arithmetic and what are the broad area of their weakness. Fraction as a topic is continuing from class III to class VIII. Thus, to know how far the student has understood the basic concept of fraction and decimal, students of upper primary level are the best ones to choose as they have to enter at secondary stage and their weaknesses in basic mathemathics can affect their study at secondary level and also at higher level. Hence, investigators had selected upper primary school students for the present study.

Mathematics contributes a great deal to the development of students. It deals with simple calculation to higher reasoning. The students who are able to understand basics of mathematics including addition, subtraction, multiplication and division with numbers will be able to use these further in day to day life. Also there exists a vertical relationship between the concepts learnt at primary stage and the concepts to be learnt at secondary stage. There is a demand for sound base at primary level in mathematics which in turn enhances the further learning of mathematics. The research studies of Kohari & Gupta (2000) and Sashidharan (1992) have proved that academic achievement in mathematics is less or average. George (1993) observed in his study that students showed remarkable deficit in the possession of basics of mathematics. Rastogi (1983) supports the same by indicating one of the important causes of backwardness in mathematics was poor performance over basic arithmetic skills.

Thus, it appears that majority of students is weak in mathematics for more than one reason but it is also evident that such students have poor basics. There is an urgent need to identify such basics along with their causes. Many a time students are not able to understand the particular concept, which ultimately leads to such weakness and same will result in low achievement in mathematics. Thus the present study was an attempt to identify such basic concepts of fractions and decimals which students are unable to understand. Further probable causes were identified for such weakness. Such causes are helpful to the teachers to plan their lessons with major focus on understanding particular concept.

Statement of the Problem: On the basis of the above the investigator selected the following theme for the study.
Learning difficulties on fractions and decimals: A study on the Upper Primary School student.

Objectives

1. To identify concepts in decimal and fractions where students have lack of understanding.
2. To identify causes for lack of understanding of these concepts.

For the present study, learning difficulties means the errors committed by the standard VI & VII students in selected fractions and decimals content of mathematics and causes behind these errors.

Delimitation of the Study

- The study was delimited to the Vadodara city of the Gujarat State of India.
- The study was further delimited to the non-granted Gujarati medium upper primary school of Vadodara city following the syllabus recommended by Gujarat Primary Education.

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- Further, the present study was delimited to only VI and VII standard students of the academic year 2010-11.

Research Design Methods

Descriptive survey method was employed for the investigation.

Population and the Sample

All the 191 non-granted Gujarati medium upper primary schools of the Vadodara city (*DEO Report of Vadodara City, 2011*) constituted population for the present investigation. All the students of standard VI and VII studying in 191 non-granted Gujarati medium upper primary schools of the Vadodara city constituted population for the present investigation.

For selecting a required number of upper primary schools, six schools were drawn randomly from the 191 non-granted Gujarati medium upper primary schools of Vadodara City (*DEO Report of Vadodara City, 2011*). All the students of class VI and VII of the selected six non-granted Gujarati medium upper primary schools of Vadodara city were selected for the present investigation. Thus, the students were selected using cluster sampling technique. Total 553 students were selected for the present investigation. The following Table 1 presents school wise sample size taken under the present investigation.

Table 1: School wise Sample Size of the Students

Sl. No.	Name of the Upper Primary School	Standard		Total No. of Students
		VI	VIII	
1.	Hill Memorial School	41	48	89
2.	R.C. Patel Navyug Vidyalaya	44	38	82
3.	Shree Pratap High School	54	44	98
4.	Shree T.R. Patel Vidyalaya	29	70	99
5.	University Experimental School	41	49	90
6.	Urmi Vidyalaya	45	50	95
	Total			
	Grand Total	254	299	553

Tools

For the present investigation, investigators constructed a diagnostic test in order to study the learning difficulties on fractions and decimals among the the students of

upper primary schools. The investigators had consulted fifteen Mathematics teachers of the upper primary schools and identified the concepts on fractions and decimals in which the students were facing difficulties and unable to understand about that concepts. The investigators went through the standard III to standard VII Mathematics textbooks and common content regarding the fractions and decimals were identified. Based on that, the test items was decided. Preparation of the test items were done by keeping the criteria given by Rastogi (1991) for constructing the items of test. The test items were given to five experts in the field of mathematics education for validation. The experts were satisfied with the test but they suggested omitting some of the common test items as the test was lengthy for the upper primary school students. So, twenty items were dropped including its sub-items by taking care that only repeated or same contents were deleted. Thus, final version of the test was made containing thirty items. The prepared test was tried out on a group of 30 students of the upper primary schools other than the sampled schools. The pilot study helped the investigators in preparing a final version of the test. Based on their responses with respect to understanding of questions, language used, the investigators made necessary modifications in the test items. Thus considering the above mentioned points final version of the test was prepared. The time taken in completing the test by the selected group of students of the pilot study was one hour so for the test administration total time of one hour was decided for administration of the test.

Data Collection

For data collection, the investigators contacted the school principals of the selected six upper primary schools. After fixing the time for conducting a test in schools, investigators visited the selected six upper primary schools as per the date and time given for collecting data. All the students of standard VI and VII present during the data collection time were called in single classroom for test purpose. The investigators also requested the mathematics teacher for assisting in conducting the test. Before conducting the test, the investigators had introduced about the investigation in brief, purpose of test, time limit and necessary instruction related to the test were given to the students. After that, test copies were distributed among the students. After an hour, all the answer sheets were collected from the students.

Analysis of Data and Results

The collected data were analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively. In order to analyze the data for the first objective, frequency and percentage were calculated to note down the correct and incorrect responses of the students in each item. A table was prepared, in which question number, correct responses, incorrect responses of the students and common difficulties/frequent difficulties faced the students were also noted down. To achieve the second objective, the investigators prepared a common table for

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Q. No.	1	2 (a)	(b)	3 (a)	(b)	4 (a)	(b)
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all the 30 items. Identified causes of lack of understanding in particular items of fractions and decimals were analyzed in content form against the every items of the test.

Table 2 shows the item wise correct, incorrect responses of the students and causes of lack of understanding about the particular concept.

Table 2: Item wise Correct, Incorrect and Causes of Lack of Understanding

Q. No.	Item	Incorrect Response	Correct Response	Causes of Lack of Understanding
1	Convert Shaded figure into fraction	$3, \frac{6}{3}, \frac{6}{3},$ $11, \frac{24}{13}, \frac{11}{13},$ $\frac{4}{4}, \frac{8}{4}$ (30.23%)	$\frac{3}{6}, \frac{13}{24}, \frac{4}{8}$ (68.03%)	Student do not have ability to identify numerator and denominator in shading figure. The most common error of students in this item is unshaded parts divided by shaded parts or vice versa.
2 (a)	Convert Fraction into Shaded Figure	 (71.93%)	Student draw rectangle and divided the parts as per the numerator and denominator and they shaded parts of denominator. There is misconception about proper fraction; they understand that denominator is more shaded parts than numerator.	
(b)	 (69.03%)			
3 (a)	Point out Numerator & Denominator in Fraction	Numerator : 3 Denominator: 2 (11.67%)	Nume : 2 Deno : 3 (83.37%)	Students do not have knowledge about the numerator place is at top and denominator place is at bottom in fraction.
(b)		Numerator : 17 Denominator: 14 (12.10%)	Nume : 14 Deno : 17 (82.51%)	
4 (a)	Write Fraction Arrange in Classify into	$4, 4, \frac{4}{16}, \frac{16}{4}$ (11.23%)	$4/4, 1$ (82.51%)	Student do not have knowledge about the numerator place is at top and denominator place is at bottom in fraction. They do not understand the abbreviation of numerator and denominator as N and D.
(b)		$\frac{5}{3}, \frac{3}{15}$ (11.02%)	$3/5,$ (82.28%)	

Q. No.	Item	Correct Response	Incorrect Response	Correct Response	Causes for Lack of Understanding
5 (a)	Find out Equivalent from the given pair of Fraction	Equivalent Fraction $\frac{4}{25} = \frac{19}{100}$ not equivalent	$\frac{4}{25} = \frac{19}{100}$ $\frac{10}{100} = \frac{4}{25}$	(32.83%)	Student do not have knowledge about the how to cancel the numerator from denominator in fraction and vice versa.
5 (b)		Equivalent Fraction $\frac{100}{100} = \frac{100}{100}$	Not Equivalent Fraction $\frac{133}{16} \neq \frac{100}{100}$	(29.38%)	(50.54%)
6 (a)	Replace with Correct Number in Place of*	$\frac{1}{24} = \frac{3}{48}$ $\frac{1}{48} = \frac{3}{48}$ $\frac{3}{48} = \frac{3}{48}$	$\frac{4}{60} = \frac{5}{15}$ $\frac{4}{60} = \frac{5}{15}$ $\frac{5}{60} = \frac{4}{60}$ $\frac{4}{60} = \frac{5}{60}$ $\frac{5}{30} = \frac{4}{60}$	(19.44%)	(66.74%)
6 (b)		Student do not have knowledge about how to cancel the numerator from denominator and vice versa in fraction and how to equivalent fraction.	$\frac{2}{9} = \frac{9}{12} = \frac{16}{16} = \frac{27}{27}$ $\frac{3}{9} = \frac{12}{12} = \frac{16}{16} = \frac{27}{27}$	(42.12%)	(43.63%)
7 (a)		Student do not have clarity of the concept of Proper Fraction, Improper fraction and mixed fraction. They do not classify easily. Students easily identify mixed fraction than proper and improper fraction. There is misconception about proper fraction and improper fraction.	$\frac{7}{4} = \frac{4}{3}$ $\frac{4}{3} = \frac{3}{4}$	(46.22%)	(41.26%)
7 (b)	Proper, Improper & Mixed Fraction	$\frac{1}{3} = \frac{4}{12}$ $\frac{3}{4} = \frac{7}{5}$	$\frac{1}{3} = \frac{4}{12}$ $\frac{3}{4} = \frac{7}{5}$	(45.36%)	(42.55%)
7 (c)		$\frac{1}{3} = \frac{4}{12}$ $\frac{3}{4} = \frac{7}{5}$ $\frac{4}{3} = \frac{2}{1}$ $\frac{3}{2} = \frac{6}{4}$ $\frac{1}{2} = \frac{3}{6}$ $\frac{1}{5} = \frac{2}{10}$	$\frac{1}{3} = \frac{4}{12}$ $\frac{3}{4} = \frac{7}{5}$ $\frac{4}{3} = \frac{2}{1}$ $\frac{3}{2} = \frac{6}{4}$ $\frac{1}{2} = \frac{3}{6}$ $\frac{1}{5} = \frac{2}{10}$	(22.90%)	(63.50%)
8 (a)		Causes for Lack of Understanding			
8 (b)					
8 (c)					
9 (a)					
9 (b)					
10 (a)					
10 (b)					

Q. No.	Item	Incorrect Response	Correct Response	Causes of Lack of Understanding
8 (a)	Convert Fraction into Mixed Fraction	$4\frac{4}{3}, 3\frac{4}{4}, 1\frac{19}{4}$ (22.89%)	$4\frac{4}{3}$ (67.69%)	Student have lack of concept clarity about conversion of improper fraction into mixed fraction. Students do not know about the Least Common Multiple (LCM) to find out the mixed fraction.
		$6\frac{5}{6}, 6\frac{5}{3}, 5\frac{3}{6}, 1\frac{23}{6}, 6\frac{3}{5}$ (23.76%)	$3\frac{5}{6}$ (65.44%)	
		$7\frac{2}{5}, 2\frac{5}{7}, 7\frac{5}{2}, 1\frac{37}{7}, 2\frac{5}{7}$ (21.60%)	$5\frac{2}{6}$ (66.30%)	
9 (a)	Convert Mixed Fraction into Improper Fraction	$\frac{85}{17}, \frac{27}{17}, \frac{20}{17}, \frac{90}{17}, 90$ (22.68%)	$\frac{100}{17}$ (67.38%)	Student do not have concept clarity about conversion of mixed fraction into improper fraction. Students do not know about Converting a mixed number to an improper fraction by using following formula $a\frac{c}{d} = \frac{ad+c}{d}$
		$\frac{98}{19}, \frac{18}{19}, 90$ (24.84%)	$\frac{99}{19}$ (66.09%)	
10 (a)	Ascending Order	$\frac{8}{12}, \frac{6}{12}, \frac{5}{12}$ (15.56%)	$\frac{5}{12}, \frac{6}{12}, \frac{8}{12}$ (84.24%)	Student do not have concept clarity about smaller and greater fraction as they could not arrange in ascending order.
		$\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{5}$ (65.88%)	$\frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}$ (32.18%)	

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Q. No.	Item	Incorrect Response	Correct Response	Causes of Lack of Understanding
11 (a)	Arrange in Descending Order	(70.85%) $\frac{2}{2}, \frac{2}{2}, \frac{4}{3}, \frac{5}{7}, \frac{7}{7}$	$\frac{2}{2}, \frac{2}{2}, \frac{4}{3}, \frac{5}{7}, \frac{7}{7}$	Student do not have concept clarity about greater and smaller fractions as well as ascending order and descending order. Students do not know about greater than and less than for ascending and descending order.
		(42.33%) $\frac{2}{7}, \frac{3}{7}, \frac{4}{7}, \frac{6}{7}, \frac{7}{7}$	$\frac{2}{7}, \frac{3}{7}, \frac{4}{7}, \frac{6}{7}, \frac{7}{7}$	
12 (a)	Point out Greater Fraction from the Pair of Fraction	$\frac{3}{2}, \frac{11}{2}$	$\frac{3}{3}, \frac{13}{3}$	Student do not have concept clarity about greater fraction and were unable to convert mixed fraction into improper fraction and error in performing the multiplication.
		(86.17%) $\frac{4}{7}, \frac{4}{20}$	(11.88%) $\frac{4}{8}, \frac{4}{12}$	
13 (a)	Arrange in Descending Order	$\frac{19}{1}, \frac{7}{9}, \frac{15}{15}, \frac{3}{8}, \frac{5}{19}, \frac{4}{7}, \frac{2}{9}, \frac{4}{8}, \frac{4}{15}$	$\frac{19}{15}, \frac{7}{9}, \frac{1}{9}, \frac{1}{15}, \frac{3}{8}, \frac{5}{19}, \frac{4}{7}, \frac{2}{9}, \frac{4}{8}$	Student do not have concept clarity about finding the LCM as well as conversion of mixed fraction into improper fraction. This item was found hard to solve by the students and they have done more mistake to multiply and LCM.
		(87.90%) $\frac{5}{5}, \frac{4}{8}, \frac{2}{8}, \frac{4}{8}, \frac{8}{8}, \frac{3}{8}$	(2.16%) $\frac{5}{15}, \frac{4}{19}, \frac{2}{7}, \frac{3}{9}, \frac{4}{8}, \frac{4}{8}$	
14 (a)	Put Correct Numerals in the of*	$\frac{4}{7} = \frac{8}{8}, \frac{4}{7} = \frac{40}{40}, \frac{4}{8} = \frac{8}{8}, \frac{4}{7} = \frac{35}{35}, \frac{4}{8} = \frac{8}{8}$		Student do not have concept clarity about equivalent fraction. Students do not know about converting a mixed fraction into an improper fraction to make an equivalent fraction.
		(25.48%) $\frac{4}{8} = \frac{8}{8}, \frac{4}{7} = \frac{35}{35}, \frac{4}{8} = \frac{8}{8}$		
15 (a)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{9}{9}, \frac{27}{27}, 1$	$\frac{9}{9}, \frac{9}{9}, 1$	Student have misconceptions about addition of fraction. They have added the denominator in place of using LCM or common denominator.
		(39.96%) $\frac{120}{37}, \frac{40}{37}, \frac{40}{36}, \frac{40}{39}$	(43.42%) $\frac{120}{37}, \frac{40}{37}, \frac{40}{36}, \frac{40}{39}$	
19 (b)	Put Correct Numerals in the of*	$\frac{66}{200} = \frac{3}{200}, \frac{12}{200} = \frac{3}{200}, \frac{66}{3} = \frac{3}{3}$	$\frac{66}{2} = \frac{3}{200}, \frac{12}{2} = \frac{3}{200}, \frac{66}{3} = \frac{3}{3}$	
		(21.60%) $\frac{66}{3} = \frac{3}{3}, \frac{12}{200} = \frac{3}{200}, \frac{66}{3} = \frac{3}{3}$	(69.33%) $\frac{66}{2} = \frac{3}{200}, \frac{12}{2} = \frac{3}{200}, \frac{66}{3} = \frac{3}{3}$	

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Q. No.	Item	Incorrect Response	Correct Response	Causes of Lack of Understanding
16 (a)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{13}{72}, \frac{13}{45}$ (70.42%)	$\frac{49}{135}$ (16.41%)	Student have misconceptions about addition of fraction. They have added the denominator in place of using LCM. Without using LCM, Addition of fraction is solved by students. Also they were not able to find correct LCM.
(b)		$\frac{64}{61}, \frac{61}{36}, \frac{61}{56}, \frac{61}{50}$ (72.14%)	$\frac{341}{72}, 4 \frac{53}{72}$ (12.09%)	
17 (a)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{50}{15}, \frac{49}{71}, \frac{49}{17}, 3 \frac{5}{15}, 50$ (76.46%)	$4 \frac{4}{15}, \frac{64}{15}$ (7.99%)	Student have misconceptions about addition of mixed fraction. They have made mistake to convert mixed fraction into improper fraction. Also they were not able to find correct LCM.
(b)		$\frac{51}{11}, \frac{49}{33}, 100, \frac{100}{33}$ (69.12%)	$6 \frac{4}{33}, \frac{202}{33}$ (12.09%)	
18 (a)	Simplification of Fraction	$1, \frac{5}{4}, \frac{1}{0} = 1$ (25.05%)	$\frac{1}{4}$ (63.72%)	Student have misconceptions about subtraction of fraction. They have done mistake to subtract denominator from denominator, when denominator is same.
(b)		$\frac{1}{0} = 1, \frac{0}{1}, 1, \frac{9}{10}$ (23.54%)	$\frac{1}{10}$ (63.94%)	
19 (a)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{2}{5}$ (57.66%)	$\frac{11}{84}$ (25.92%)	Student have misconception about subtraction of fraction. They have done mistake in subtracting denominator from denominator, when denominator is different. They were unable to solve the problem rightly. They do not know to use LCM
(b)		$\frac{6}{9}, \frac{3}{12}$ (51.84%)	$\frac{1}{4}$ (28.73%)	
(c)		$\frac{6}{8}$ (66.09%)	$\frac{1}{16}$ (14.48%)	

Q. No.	Item	Correct Response	Incorrect Response	Causes of Lack of Understanding
20 (a)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{3}{3}, \frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{3}{0}, \frac{3}{3}, \frac{1}{2}$	Student have misconception about subtraction of fraction. They have done mistake to convert mixed fraction into improper fraction and then they have subtracted from denominator. They have not used LCM of fraction.
20 (b)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{5}{6}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{10}{38}, \frac{10}{10}, \frac{10}{10}, \frac{5}{5}$	$\frac{5}{10}, \frac{6}{10}, \frac{10}{38}, \frac{10}{10}, \frac{10}{10}, \frac{5}{5}$	Student have misconception about multiplication of fraction. They have done mistake to multiply with numerator and denominator both.
21 (a)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{2}{5}, \frac{4}{24}, \frac{5}{53}$	$\frac{5}{28}, \frac{5}{5}, \frac{5}{5}$	Student have misconception about multiplication of fraction. They have done mistake to multiply with numerator and denominator both.
21 (b)	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{6}{3}, \frac{9}{12}$	$\frac{5}{28}, \frac{5}{5}, \frac{5}{5}$	Student have misconception about multiplication of fraction. They have done mistake to multiply with numerator and denominator both.
22 (a)	Fill in the blanks	75, 11.44%, 1, 16, 10	10 $\frac{1}{2}$, 10.5 $\frac{5}{28}$	Student have not clarity about division of fraction. Students do not use to know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.
22 (b)	Fill in the blanks	14.2, 44.51%	10 $\frac{1}{2}$, 10.5 $\frac{5}{28}$	Student have not clarity about division of fraction. Students do not use to know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.
22 (c)	Fill in the blanks	15, 1, 1, 8, 4, 1, 4	45, 1, 13, 32, 1, 12	Student have not clarity about division of fraction. Students do not use to know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.
22 (d)	Fill in the blanks	6, 4, 30, 14, 34.98%	4, 32, 1, 12, 14.04%	Student have not clarity about division of fraction. Students do not use to know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.
22 (e)	Fill in the blanks	7, 2, 42.55%	8, 2, 3, 30.02%	Student do not have clarity about division of fraction. Students do not use to know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.
23 (a)	Division of Fraction	$\frac{7}{2}, \frac{8}{4}$	$\frac{8}{2}, \frac{2}{3}$	Student do not have clarity about division of fraction. Students do not use to know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.
23 (b)	Division of Fraction	$\frac{6}{24}, \frac{7}{1}, \frac{6}{7}, \frac{7}{7}$	$\frac{6}{6}, \frac{7}{7}$	Student do not have clarity about division of fraction. Students do not use to know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.
24				
25 (a)				
25 (b)				
26 (a)				
26 (b)				
27 (a)				
27 (b)				

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Q. No.	Item	Incorrect Response	Correct Response	Causes of Lack of Understanding
24	Simplification of Fraction	$\frac{24}{8}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{8}{8}$ (47.52%)	$\frac{16}{15}, 1, \frac{1}{15}$ (19.44%)	Student do not have clarity, when simplification of two process together such as addition and division of fraction. They have done first addition and then division. They do not use to know about the sequence of Division. Multiplication, Addition and Subtraction, when there is simplification of mathematical process.
25 (a)	Expression of decimal figure into Fraction	$\frac{23}{1}, \frac{23}{10}, \frac{10}{23}, \frac{32}{100}, \frac{0}{23}, \frac{32}{1}$ (76.46%)	$\frac{23}{100}$ (76.46%)	Student do not have concept clarity about decimal fraction and simple fraction. They have done mistake to convert decimal fraction into simple fraction.
(b)		$\frac{576}{576}, \frac{576}{1000}, 576, \frac{576}{1}$ (48.16%)	$\frac{576576}{1000}$ $576, \frac{576}{1000}$ (27.21%)	
26 (a)	Expression of decimal figure into Fraction	0.85, 0.59, 58 (10.37%)	0.58 (51.86%)	Student do not have clarity about addition of decimal fraction as well as place value system. Students forgot to put decimal point after addition of the fraction.
(b)		11058, 11658 (9.92%)	11.058 (83.59%)	
27 (a)		0015, 15 (10.15%)	0.15 (87.91%)	Student do not have clarity about subtraction of decimal fraction as well as place value system. Students forgot to put decimal point after subtraction of the fraction.
(b)	Subtraction of decimal fraction	8.75, 0.10, 1.35 (39.10%)	1.25 (56.80%)	

Q. No.	Item	Incorrect Response	Correct Response	Causes of Lack of Understanding
28 (a)	Fill in the blank	500, 500, 0.055, 5500, 5.500	550	Student do not have clarity about multiplication of decimal fraction as well as place value system. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in multiplication of the fraction. They were also confuse to shift decimal point to the right by as many places as the number of zeros in the multiplier.
		5000, 5000, 0.055, 5500	5500	Student do not have clarity about multiplication of decimal fraction as well as place value system. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in multiplication of the fraction. Also Students do not know about the number of decimal places in the product is equal to the sum of number of decimal places in the product
29 (a)	Multiplication	2.40, 420, 1482, 4.3	4.2	Student do not have clarity about multiplication of decimal places in both the given numbers.
		5.69, 1569, 15.69, 6.90, 1.569	1,569	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.
29 (b)	Multiplication	5.69, 1569, 15.69, 6.90, 1.569	1,569	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.
		2.40, 420, 1482, 4.3	4.2	Student do not have clarity about multiplication of decimal places in both the given numbers.
30 (a)	Division of Fraction	3500, $5\frac{3}{100}$, 3.20	0.035	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.
		87500, 0.875, 8.750	0.0875	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.
		875000, 20.00875, 12	0.00875	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.
		875000, 20.00875, 12	0.00875	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.
30 (d)	Division of Fraction	400, 25	0.004	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.
		400, 25	0.004	Student do not have clarity about division of decimal fraction by 100 and 1000. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in division of the fraction. They were also confused to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.

(Figure in the parenthesis indicate the percentage of incorrect and correct responses)

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Major Finding of the Study

On the basis of the analysis of data, the major findings of the present study were been drawn objective wise as follows.

Findings of objective I (Identification of Concepts in Decimal and Fractions where Students have Lack of Understanding)

- 30.23 percent of the students were not able to convert the shaded figure into fraction.
- 26.13 percent and 27.22 percent of the students were not able to convert the given fraction into shaded figure.
- 11.67 percent and 12.10 percent of the students were not able to point out the numerator and denominator in the fraction.
- 11.23 percent and 11.02 percent of the students were unable to write fraction from the given numerator and denominator.
- 32.83 percent and 29.38 percent of the students were unable to find the correct fraction from the given pair.
- 19.44 percent, 42.12 percent and 50.33 percent of the students were unable to replace the correct number.
- 46.22 percent, 45.36 percent and 22.90 percent of the students failed to classify the given items.
- 22.89 percent, 23.76 percent and 21.60 percent of the students were unable to convert the given fraction into mixed fractions.
- 22.68 percent and 24.84 percent of the students failed to convert the given mixed fractions into improper fractions.
- 15.56 percent and 65.88 percent of the students were unable to arrange the given items in ascending order.
- 70.85 percent and 42.33 percent of the students failed to arrange the items in descending order.
- 22.25 percent and 86.17 percent of the students failed to point out the greater fraction.
- 87.90 percent and 85.10 percent of the students were unable to arrange the given items in descending order.
- 25.48 percent and 21.60 percent of the students failed to place correctly the numerals in the place of given*.
- 39.96 percent and 43.42 percent of the students were unable to simplify the given fractions.

- Majority of them i.e. 70.42 percent and 72.14 percent of the students were unable to simplify the given items.
 - Majority of them i.e. 76.46 percent and 69.12 percent of the students were unable to simplify the given items.
 - 25.05 percent and 23.54 percent of the students were unable to simplify the given items.
 - 57.66 percent, 51.84 percent and 66.09 percent of the students were unable to simplify the given items correctly.
 - More than half of them i.e. 57.88 percent and 57.24 percent of the students were unable to simplify the given items of fractions.
 - 32.40 percent and 39.52 percent of the students were unable to simplify the given items of fractions.
 - 11.44 percent, 47.30 percent, 44.51 percent, 57.66 percent and 34.98 percent of the students were unable to answer the given items related to the division of the fractions.
 - 42.55 percent and 31.10 percent of the students were unable to divide the given items of fractions.
 - Nearly half of them i.e. 47.52 percent of the students were unable to convert the given decimal fraction into the fraction.
 - 30.88 percent and 48.16 percent of the students were unable to convert the given decimal fraction into the fraction.
 - 10.37 percent and 9.92 percent of the students were unable to do the addition of the given fractions.
 - 10.15 percent and 39.10 percent of the students were unable to subtract the given decimal fraction.
 - 39.79 percent, 50.54 percent and 49.02 percent of the students were unable to give the correct answer of the multiplication of the fractions.
 - 31.74 percent and 46.66 percent of the students were unable to multiply the given fractions.
 - 39.96 percent, 44.50 percent, 47.94 percent and 42.55 percent of the students were unable to convert the given mixed fractions into improper fractions.
- Finding of object II (Identification of Causes for Lack of Understanding of the Concepts of Fractions and Decimals)**
- Students do not have ability to identify numerator and denominator in shading figure. The most common error of students in this item is un-shaded parts divided by shaded parts or vice versa.

- Students had drawn rectangle and divided the parts as per the numerator and denominator and they shaded parts of denominator. There is misconception about proper fraction; they understand that denominator is more shaded parts than numerator.
- Students do not have knowledge about the numerator place is at top and denominator place is at bottom in fraction.
- Students do not have knowledge about the numerator place is at top and denominator place is at bottom in fraction. They do not understand the abbreviation of numerator and denominator as N and D.
- Students do not have knowledge about how to cancel the numerator from denominator in fraction and vice versa.
- Students do not have clarity of the concept of Proper fraction, Improper fraction and mixed fraction. They do not classify easily. Students easily identify mixed fraction than proper and improper fraction. There is misconception about proper fraction and improper fraction.
- Students have lack of concept clarity about conversion of improper fraction into mixed fraction. Students do not use to know about the Least Common Multiple (LCM) to find out the mixed fraction.
- Students do not have concept clarity about conversion of mixed fraction into improper fraction. Students do not know about Converting a mixed number to an improper fraction by using following formula:
$$a \frac{c}{d} = \frac{ad + c}{d}$$
- Students do not have concept clarity about greater fraction and smaller fraction as well as ascending order and descending order. Students do not know about greater than and less than for ascending and descending order.
- Students do not have concept clarity about finding the LCM as well as conversion of mixed fraction into improper fraction. This item was found hard to be solved by students and they have done more mistake to multiply and LCM.
- Students do not have concept clarity about equivalent fraction. Students do not know about Converting a mixed fraction into an improper fraction to make an equivalent fraction.
- Students have misconception about addition of fraction. They have added the denominator in place of using LCM or common denominator.
- Students have misconception about addition of fraction. They have added the denominator in place of using LCM. Without using LCM, Addition of fraction is solved by students. Also they were not able to find correct LCM.
- Students have misconception about addition of fraction. They have done mistake to subtract denominator from denominator, when denominator is different. They were unable to solve the problem rightly. They do not know about using LCM.

Students have misconception about subtraction of fraction. They have done mistake to convert mixed fraction into improper fraction and then they have subtracted denominator from denominator. They have not used LCM of fraction.

Students have misconception about multiplication of fraction. They have done mistake to multiply with numerator and denominator both.

Students have not clarity about division of fraction. Students do not know about Division is the Reverse of Multiplication.

Students have not clarity, when simplification of two process together such as addition and division of fraction. They have done first addition and then division.

They do not know about the sequence of Division, Multiplication, Addition and Subtraction, when there is simplification of mathematical process.

Students do not have concept clarity about decimal fraction and simple fraction.

They have done mistake to convert decimal fraction into simple fraction.

Students do not have clarity about addition of decimal fraction as well as place value system. Students forgot to put decimal point after addition of the fraction.

Students do not have clarity about subtraction of decimal fraction as well as place value system. Students forgot to put decimal point after subtraction of the fraction.

Students do not have clarity about multiplication of decimal fraction as well as place value system. Students forgot to put decimal point at correct place in multiplication of the fraction. Also students do not use to know about the number of decimal places in the product is equal to the sum of number of decimal places in both the given numbers.

Students do not have clarity about division of the fraction. Also confuse these were to shift decimal point to the left by as many places as the number of zeros in the divisor.

Discussion

The result of the present study revealed that the students were found weak in the concepts of fractions and decimal which they have already learnt. Also the present study supports the findings of the previous researches of Koithari & Shelat (2011), Goel (1996), Sarla (1990), and Raman (1989). One of the main reasons for the weak performances of the students was that they were weak in applying the rules of addition, multiplication and division as most of the students were unable to simplify the given fractions. The study of Pal (1997) also supports this finding. The study also reveals that majority of the students was unable to arrange the fractions in ascending or descending order. The causes of their lack of understanding in the concepts of fractions and decimal

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were of misconception in the place of numerator and denominator, misconception in proper and improper fraction, lack of knowledge of LCM, misconception in addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of fraction, no concept clarity in the sequence of Division, Multiplication, Addition and Subtraction and lack of concept clarity in decimal. It showed that students are unable to link the theory with the practical examples. Also, it was observed that the students lack in basic arithmetic skills as majority of the students was not able to multiply, add or even subtract the two digits number. Above all the raised problem needs immediate attention and remediation.

Suggestions for Teachers

- i) It was found that the upper primary school students were weak in the concept of fraction and decimal. So it is necessary for the teachers to know the entry behaviour of the students. For that the teacher can conduct a test before starting the new concept as this can help the teacher to know how far the students had adhere the related concepts. Until and unless they do not clear the doubt of the students, they should not move ahead with the new concept. As vertical relationship exist in concepts, without the understanding of past knowledge it will be difficult for the students to progress ahead. Hence it is very well required to clear of doubt of related concept/past learned concepts for very well understanding of the new concepts for longer period of time.
- ii) It was found that the students forget the rules and laws which they have learned in the past years. So a teacher should do recapitulation of those laws or rules before and after applying these.
- iii) As students were not able to apply their theoretical knowledge into practical form like solving the word problem, so teacher should try to link the concept with real life situations and may give daily life similar examples which may be related to the word problem for better understanding of the concept.
- iv) Students were found weak in important concepts like increasing or decreasing, adding or subtracting fractions, classifying the proper & improper fractions etc. So diagnostic and remediation programme can be prepared for the students who have actually scored less in the content.
- v) MLL based approach can help for understanding the concept.
- vi) A PLM can be made in order to help the students who scored low in the content.

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